

Tunneling Atomic Force Microscopy Characterization of Cuprous Oxide Thin Films

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Abstract—In this work we characterized thermally grown cuprous oxide thin films using tunneling atomic force microscopy (TUNA) and optical reflection measurements. Significant hysteresis was observed in the I-V curves measured at the nanometer contact under various bias voltages. Histogram analysis of the barrier voltage distribution indicated the barrier height is related to electrochemical potentials for oxidation/ reduction of copper atoms. Changes in chemical state of copper atoms were identified by optical reflectance measurements in the UV-VIS-NIR wavelength region. The peak shift observed in the optical reflection measurements from the short to the long wavelength is attributed to the quantum size confinement effects of the nanometer-scale cuprous particles formed in the films. The grain size, including surface roughness, was measured by topographic AFM imaging. The fluctuations in the I-V measurements are likely due to changes of electrochemical properties of cuprous ions in the film, including the grain size distribution. The asymmetric distribution in the barrier height may indicate that a different probability for injecting an electron in and withdrawing an electron from the films.

I. INTRODUCTION

Solid state transistors have revolutionized the world by providing us with cheap and fast methods of data processing. However, the silicon-based transistors as they are currently designed are approaching size limitations largely due to dielectric breakdown at sub-100 nanometer scales. Memristors are among many other possible solutions to this problem.

Leon Chua first developed the concept of the memristor in the 1970s. He identified the incompleteness of the electric circuit theory and described a fourth element that would relate charge to flux, named as memristor [1]. Strukov *et al* [2] reported a memristor device in 2008, which was based on thin-film TiO₂ with oxygen vacancies that migrated through the lattice to switch the material between high and low resistive states.

Copper, inexpensive and non-hazardous, is known as a staple of current electronics. The copper atoms when they are reduced into cuprous ions (e.g., Cu¹⁺) are used in ionic conductors for its high ionic mobility. It has been reported that some cuprous-oxide systems exhibited memristive properties while the memristive mechanisms are not well understood [3]. In this work, we studied memristive properties of the copper oxide-based system at nanometer length scales. We prepared thermally-grown Cu₂O thin

films and characterized electronic properties of partially oxidized thin copper films using tunneling atomic force microscopy (TUNA) and optical reflection measurements.

II. EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

The properties of the thin films were studied using tunneling atomic force microscopy (TUNA) and optical reflectance measurement. A Veeco Dimension V atomic force microscopy equipped with a tunneling current module was used to collect I-V curves of thin copper films, as illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Tunneling atomic force microscopy measurement of the I-V curve of copper/cuprous oxide/platinum-iridium (MIM) structures on a silicon wafer. A bias voltage ranging from -3.5 to +3.5 was applied between the gold contact and the conductive AFM tip.

A thin layer of copper roughly 100 nm in thickness was deposited on silicon wafers using a Denton 18 plasma deposition system in an argon atmosphere at a pressure of 3.7mTorr. The wafers were transferred to an evaporation chamber where roughly 100nm of gold was evaporated through a shadow mask to protect the gold electrode. The samples were then diced and oxidized for varying times in a quartz tube furnace at 125°C with a mixture of 50/50 oxygen/argon flowing through the tube at 20psi. The copper electrode was connected to the tunneling module through a gold bonded wire and the protective gold film, which prevented the copper under the gold from oxidation. The platinum-iridium on the TUNA probe tip in contact with the oxidized copper film served as the other electrode.

Optical microscopy images of the samples treated in the oxidizing atmosphere for different times are shown in Figure 2. The color of the copper film gradually turned into pink until the time of heat treatment was increased to 120 minutes, at which the sample started to show light grey with scattered pink spots.

Figure 2. Optical microscopy images of the reduced thin copper films showing changes in color due to oxidation. From top left to bottom right, oxidation times were: 0 seconds, 45 seconds, 90 seconds, 135 seconds, 5 minutes, 10 minutes, 15 minutes, 30 minutes, 45 minutes, 60 minutes, and 120 minutes.

A platinum-iridium coated antimony doped silicon (SCM-PIC probe, Veeco) was used in this work. The cantilever has a nominal spring constant of 0.2N/m with a minimum at 0.1N/m and a maximum of 0.4N/m. A force plot was acquired on each sample before I-V measurements were conducted. The deflection ‘setpoint’ was adjusted to ensure a constant load at 10nN was applied on each sample with an estimated contact area of 4nm². Two sets of I-V data were collected. The first set of data was measured at bias voltages from -3.5 to 3.5 V continuous ramps at a frequency of 0.25Hz and current sensitivity of 10pA/V for 76 I-V trace captures. The same experimental parameters were repeated at 5 different locations on the surface, as indicated by the XY coordinates at (0, 0), (-250nm, 250nm), (-250nm, -250nm), (250nm, 250nm), and (250nm, -250nm). The second set of data was collected at -3.5V to 3.5V continuous ramps at 0.25Hz and 100nA/V current sensitivity (the least sensitive setting) for 24 I-V trace captures. The same procedures were repeated at 5 different locations on the surface, as given by the XY coordinates at (0, 0), (250nm, 0), (250nm, 250nm), (250nm, -250nm), and (-250nm, -250nm). Topographic images of the sample surface were collected in tapping mode using a fresh silicon tip. The integral gain and proportional gain were in general set to 0.5V and 1V respectively; minor adjustments were made to improve image quality when needed. Scan settings were 0° scan angle, 1μm scan size, 512 x 512 lines, and in general 0.5Hz scan rate.

Optical reflectance measurements were performed on a Cary 5000 UV-Vis-NIR Spectrophotometer. Background measurements were first collected on a reference plate. A zero reference was also collected with no sample mounted in the machine. In order to ensure the gold on the surface did not contribute to the measured data, an appropriate aperture was used to cover the samples so that only the copper surface was exposed to the incident light beam. When collecting data, the lights in the room were extinguished in order to ensure no background light was interfering with the measurements.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The tunneling atomic force microscopy measurements generally show a non-linear I-V relationship (Figure 3, 4, and 6). At a large bias (either positive or negative), a large tunneling current passes through the contact, causing saturation in the detector at ±100pA. With decreasing the bias voltage, the tunneling current drops and approaches the zero at a critical voltage (referred to as the turning bias voltage). A noticed hysteresis is observed in the I-V curves when the bias voltage changes its polarity for the samples, heat treated for a short period of time, as shown in Figure 3. The hysteresis becomes less significant for the samples exposed to the reducing gas for a longer period of time (see Figure 4). The turning voltage in the samples fluctuated from cycle to cycle, or from location to location. The histogram of the turning voltage is shown in Figure 5 for the sample heat treated for 15 minutes in the reducing atmosphere. This distribution of the ‘turning voltage’ appeared to become narrow with increasing oxidation time. The fluctuations in the I-V curves also showed some periodicity with varying ‘turning voltage’. The periodicity seemed to decrease with increasing the oxidation time. Other observed changes include the slope, peak and valley features in the I-V curves. In some measurements, the samples show ‘on’ and ‘off’ features from a high resistance to low resistance state, accompanied with dips and peaks in the current. All of those observed fluctuations in the I-V curves are not well understood at this time.

We hypothesize that those changes are related to the particle size and grain boundaries intersecting the contact area of the tip. As oxidation time increases particle size it appears as though the number of grains intersecting the contact area decreases and consequently decreases the variability in conduction paths.

Figure 3. Typical I-V curve for the 15 minute sample. The trace data indicates the ramp from -3.5V to 3.5V and the retrace data indicates the ramp from 3.5V to -3.5V, cycled at 0.25Hz.

Figure 4. I-V curve for the 45 minute sample. The trace data indicates the ramp from -3.5V to 3.5V and the retrace data indicates the ramp from 3.5V to -3.5V, cycled at 0.25Hz.

Some of the observed behavior of the I-V relationship can be explained using the space-charge-limited-current model (SCLC). However, it is difficult to use the SCLC theory to interpret other variations in the I-V curve, such as the dips in currents and hysteresis. The histogram analysis of the observed threshold voltages indicated a possible correlation between the large fluctuations in the current and the electrochemical potential of copper. The high occurrences at ± 0.32 and ± 0.54 V, which are consistent with the electrochemical potentials of copper electrode reactions, show that the oxidation/reduction of copper may have played an important role in the I-V behavior as the cuprous ions slowly move through the samples at different bias voltages. The width of fluctuations in the threshold voltage is generally larger for the samples treated in a short period of time.

Figure 5. Histogram analysis of threshold voltages observed in the 15 minute sample.

Findings reported by Laque *et al* describes the electronic properties of a mixed ionic-electronic conductor of thin films of CuBr [4] and shows similar electronic behavior to those observed in this work. With a high initial negative voltage applied by the sample chuck, reduction occurs and a deposit of positive copper ions will build up at the copper electrode (connected electrically to the sample chuck) resulting in a space charge region within the thin film.

About the 0V point, current is reduced or stopped due to the resulting potential barrier and the insufficient electric field. When the polarity changes and overcomes the induced electric field of the resultant lattice, the process reverses with reduction occurring at the AFM tip and the current increases rapidly (see Figure 6). Any noticed lag in the retrace data may be due to the relative slow response of the ions to the changes in the electric field.

Figure 6. Illustration of mobile ions hopping through Cu_2O lattice forming filaments. The flow of ions shows correlation with the electrochemical potentials of Cu at ± 0.34 V and ± 0.52 V. The sample was heat treated for 60 minutes in the reducing atmosphere. The current sensitivity was 10pA/V .

The space charge is ultimately overcome by the applied voltage beyond the electrochemical potential. The relationship observed in this work shows similarity to but does not completely agree with work done by Dong *et al* [3] on Cu_2O showing a distinct hysteresis typical of a bi-resistive switch and memristor. This effort also does not support the notion of a singular path of filament growth, but rather suggests a random process occurring along multiple available paths.

Reflectance data was used to derive absorption information on the samples (Figure 7). The absorption features at around 600nm show the expected growth of cuprous-oxide (bandgap of 2.1eV). Additional feature near 450nm increases with relative intensity as oxidation time increases up to 15 minutes, at which point its relative intensity begins to decline. This feature may be indicative of the growth of nano-crystals of cuprous oxide in the top surface layer of the thin copper film. With increasing the particle size, the band shifts to the long wavelength, and merges into the bulk properties. Knözinger *et al* [5] reported a broad feature at about 450nm for Cu_2O nanoparticles having an average particle size of 9nm.

We estimated the particle size based on the bandgap shift in the optical spectrum using the following equation [6], $\Delta E_{\text{gap}} \approx \hbar^2 \pi^2 / 2\mu R^2$, where μ is the reduced effective mass of the electron and hole, R is the radius of the particle, and \hbar is the Planck's constant. The effective mass used in this work was $0.99m_e$ for the electron and

$0.69m_e$ for the hole. The shift in energy from the bandgap (2.1eV) and the first observed peak (~ 2.6 eV) results in a particle diameter of roughly 2.7nm. Peaks at high energies (6eV) would indicate smaller particles with diameters down to ~ 1 nm. The absence of peaks between 2.1 and 2.6eV might suggest particles in the range of 2.7nm have the optimal energetic configuration for surface tension to volume ratio. The 2.6eV peak decays in relative intensity with further oxidation after 15 minutes which may indicate the particles are getting too close together and the band structure begins to mimic bulk properties. Peaks in the energy range (>3.5 eV) grow in relative intensity with higher oxidation. This may be indicative of 1nm sized particles, but presumably of different stoichiometry than the 2.6eV particles due to their propensity to grow at higher oxidation times.

Figure 7. Absorption vs wavelength derived from reflectance data.

AFM measurements of the range in height, the average roughness, the root mean square roughness, and surface area difference indicates a trend of increasing roughness, particle size, and surface area (due to particle growth) with increasing oxidation time.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

We applied the tunneling atomic force microscopy to characterize the I-V properties of partially oxidized thin copper films on a silicon wafer. The growth of nanoparticles of cuprous oxide in the thin copper films was monitored using optical reflectance measurement in the UV-VIS-NIR wavelength region. Peak shifts in absorption were attributed to the size-dependent quantum confinement effects in the cuprous nanoparticles, formed in the top surface layer of the copper films. The I-V curves showed non-linearity and hysteresis, which may be related the grain boundaries and mixed ionic-electronic conduction. The ionic mobility appeared to be correlated with the electrochemical potentials of copper atoms. Preliminary experiment in this work shows interesting I-V properties in

the thin-film cuprous oxide that would make it a suitable candidate for future research as a novel electronic device.

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